

EXPLORING GENDER AND INSTITUTIONAL DIFFERENCE IN

METACOGNITION OF TEACHER TRAINEES. □ Dr. Manjul Gupta* Dr. Shashi Malik**

ABSTRACT

The study was carried out with a sample of 150 teacher trainees from four B.Ed. institutions affiliated to C.C. S university Meerut. Meta cognition Inventory by Punita Govil was used for determining the level of metacognition of teacher trainees. The findings of the research were that teacher trainees exhibit average metacognition; female trainees have more metacognition than male teacher trainees and institution type does not affect metacognition level of teacher trainees. The results of present study show that teacher trainees are average in metacognition, to enhance the metacognition skills in teacher trainees some training program should be developed.

Keywords : Metacognition, Gender, Institution and teacher trainees

INTRODUCTION

Today's teachers need to develop their students' abilities to prepare for life in a rapidly changing world. For this it is important for teacher trainee to have some skills so that they can also develop these skills in their students for their better lifelong learning and better problem-solving ability. For this the teacher trainee should be aware of their thinking process and the strategies which is useful to enhance such skill. The concept of what individuals think about his thinking is an increasingly significant field. Meta - cognition is the word which is used for this process. Now " Meta - cognition " is one of the latest buzz words in educational psychology. Metacognition is a regulatory system that helps a person to understand and control his or her own cognitive performance. Metacognition is closely related to teaching and learning in education. Learning depends, in part, on the effective use of basic cognitive processes such as memory and attention, the activation of relevant background knowledge, and the deployment of cognitive strategies to achieve particular goals. To ensure that the basic processes are used effectively, that the activated

knowledge is indeed relevant, and that appropriate strategies are being deployed, learners also need to have awareness and control of their cognitive processes. This higher-level cognition was given the label meta-cognition by American developmental psychologist John Flavell (1976). According to Flavell (1979, 1987), meta - cognition consists of both meta - cognitive knowledge and meta - cognitive experiences or regulation. Meta - cognitive knowledge refers to acquired knowledge about cognitive processes, knowledge that can be used to control cognitive processes. Meta - cognitive knowledge refers to one's knowledge and beliefs in his mental resources and his awareness about what to do. The ability to use meta - cognitive knowledge, on the other hand is called meta cognitive control (Ozsoy , 2007). Meta - cognitive control is related with meta - cognitive activities that help to control one's thinking or learning. We engage in meta - cognitive activities every day. Meta - cognition enables us to be successful learners, and has been associated with intelligence (e.g., Borkowski, Carr, & Pressley, 1987; Sternberg, 1984, 1986a, 1986b). Activities such as planning how to approach a given

*Assistant Professor - B.Ed. Department, KNGPG College, Gyanpur, Bhadohi

**Associate Professor - Department of Teacher Education, VMLG college, Ghaziabad

learning task, monitoring comprehension, and evaluating progress toward the completion of a task are meta - cognitive. In a landmark study, Kreutzer, Leonard, and Flavell, interviewed children in kindergarten and grades 1, 3, and 5 to determine their knowledge of how their memories work. Although Flavell and Brown are credited with introducing the term meta - cognition, they were not the first to study phenomena that was to be called meta - cognitive. Memory researchers were studying feelings of knowing and memory monitoring from at least the 1960s. In addition, Vygotsky (1896–1934) and Piaget (1896–1980) included processes as meta-cognitive in their theories of children's thinking.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PROBLEM

It is a well-accepted fact that the quality of the nation depends upon the quality of the education imparted to its citizens which in turn depends upon the quality of its personality teachers'. The term quality of teachers includes all the academic dimensions of teacher including knowledge of the content, teaching skills and teacher behaviour and teaching strategies. Due to the following three reasons, the study of meta cognition of teacher trainees is most beneficial:

1. Meta- cognitive knowledge of thinking skills is essential for introducing meta - cognitive activities in class.
2. Meta-cognitive knowledge of thinking skills is essential for the design of high-quality new learning activities because the design process requires thinking about thinking skills as explicit goals of the learning activity.
3. Meta- cognitive knowledge of thinking skills is essential for systematic teaching of higher order thinking.

The Importance of metacognition ability among the prospective teachers has become the major point of attraction in front of the researchers therefore the present study is aimed at to know the metacognition of teacher trainees in a comprehensive manner.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

EXPLORING GENDER AND INSTITUTIONAL DIFFERENCE IN METACOGNITION OF TEACHER TRAINEES.

DELIMITATIONS

1. The study was delimited to the Ghaziabad district of Uttar Pradesh only.
2. The study was delimited to only four B. Ed. Colleges of Ghaziabad.
3. The study was delimited to B.Ed. students of teacher education program.
4. The study was confined to government aided and self - financed institutions ' students not with government college students.
5. Rural areas were not taken in present research study; Therefore, the results are delimited only to urban population.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To conduct the research, the following objectives were determined:

1. To identify the meta - cognition level of teacher - trainees.
2. To compare meta - cognition of female and male teacher - trainees.
3. To compare meta - cognition of teacher - trainees of govt. aided and self – financed institution.

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant difference in meta - cognition of female and male teacher - trainees.
2. There is no significant difference in meta - cognition of teacher - trainees studying in govt. aided and self - financed institution.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive Survey Method was used.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE

The present study constituted of all B.Ed. institutions affiliated to C.C.S University, Meerut.

Sample of the study consisted of 150 teacher-trainees from two govt. aided and two self-financed institutions.

TOOL

Meta-cognition Inventory by Punita Govil was used for determining the level of metacognition of teacher trainees.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysis of the data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The data was analysed and interpreted according to the objectives and their corresponding hypotheses as discussed below:

1. METACOGNITION LEVEL OF TEACHER - TRAINEES

To explore the metacognition in teacher trainees,

two components of it were studied. Total score of metacognition was also calculated. The components of metacognition are Metacognitive Knowledge (MK) and Metacognitive Recognition (MR).

In order to study the metacognition and its constituents, descriptive measures were calculated as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive Measures of Metacognition and its constituents for Teacher trainees

S. No	Constituents of Metacognition	Range	Min	Max	M	SD	Var.
1.	Metacognition Knowledge (MK)	22	28	50	38.19	4.50	20.27
2.	Metacognition Recognition (MR)	28	40	68	52.85	6.29	39.56
	Total Metacognition	39	73	112	90.88	9.27	85.97

Table 1 clarifies the fact that teacher trainees are average in metacognition. Obtained Mean value (90.88) is under the range of 82-94 in which average individuals are grouped in test manual. Moreover, it can be said on the basis of mean values of metacognition knowledge (38.19) and metacognition recognition (52.85) that the teacher trainees have higher level of metacognition recognition than metacognition knowledge i.e., their regulation of cognition is better than knowledge of

cognitive process.

2. EFFECT OF GENDER ON METACOGNITION LEVEL OF TEACHER - TRAINEES

Testing the hypothesis 1.0: There is no significant difference in metacognition of female and male teacher trainees.

To study gender difference, t-test was applied for comparison of the mean value of metacognition. The results are depicted in the table 2.

Table 2: M, SD and t - value of Metacognition scores of teacher trainees (Gender wise)

SN	Groups	N	M	SD	t-value	P
1.	Male	50	87.78	7.926	2.97	significant at 0.01 level
2	Female	100	92.43	9.540		

It may be noted from the above table that the t - value has come out to be 2.97 that is significant at both levels of significance. Thus, the hypothesis 1.0 is rejected. Therefore, it can be inferred from the table that

both the group male teacher trainees and female teacher trainees differ significantly. Female teacher trainees seem to have more metacognition than male teacher trainees as the mean values are higher in case of female teacher

trainees as indicated in the table 2.

3. EFFECT OF INSTITUTION ON METACOGNITION LEVEL OF TEACHER - TRAINEES

Testing the hypothesis 2.0: There is no significant difference in metacognition of teacher trainees

studying in government aided and self - financed institutions.

To study the effect of institutions, t-test was applied for comparison of the mean value of metacognition. The results are depicted in the table 3.

Table3: M, SD and t - value of Metacognition scores of teacher trainees (Institute wise)

SN	Groups	N	M	SD	t-value	P
1.	Govt. Aided	62	92.11	10.614	1.371	Not significant at 0.05 level
2	Self-financed	88	90.01	8.149		

Table 3 reveals that computed t - value is 1.371 with reference to metacognition that is found non - significant at 0.05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis 2.0 is accepted. Hence, it can be said that government aided teacher trainees and self - financed teacher trainees show homogeneity in metacognition level. It further indicates that they have similar level of awareness of self-thinking process, strategy of cognition, planning to do work and evaluating the process of cognition.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

The main findings of the research in accordance with the objectives and concerning hypothesis can be summarized as under:

1. The unit of the present population secured the metacognition scores 90.88 (mean value) stands for average category in metacognition. Therefore, the major finding of the research is that teacher trainees exhibit average metacognition. They have higher level of metacognition recognition (M = 38.19) than metacognition knowledge (52.85) i.e., their regulation of cognition is better than knowledge of cognitive process.
2. Hypothesis 1.0 is rejected due to value of t (2.97). It was concluded that male teacher trainees and female teacher trainees differ significantly.

Female teacher trainees seem to have more metacognition than male teacher trainees as the mean values are higher in case of female teacher trainees. This finding can be supported by the research findings of Miller (2000) in which he found that girls have more meta - cognitive skills in Mathematics compared to boys. Also, Schommer's (1993) study investigated gender differences. According to her results girls were less likely to believe in quick learning and fixed ability than boys.

3. Hypothesis 2.0 is accepted because t- value was found as 1.371. Hence, it can be said that government aided college teacher trainees and self - financed college teacher trainees show similar level of metacognition. It further indicates that they have more or less same in awareness of self-thinking process, strategy of cognition, planning to do work and evaluating the process of cognition. It can be justified with the fact that both government aided and self-financed college teacher trainees study the same type of curriculum and have the same assignments.

DISCUSSION

Educational research is a systematic attempt to

gain a better understanding of the educational process, generally with a view to improve its efficiency. The results of present study show that teacher trainees are average in metacognition while they are being prepared for the teaching. Some training programs should be started to enhance the metacognition skills in teacher trainees. More emphasis should be given to male teacher trainees.

More researches are needed in the field of metacognition. Components of metacognition and its relationship with personality, efficiency and effectiveness of teacher trainees should be studied. Training programme for enhancement of metacognition should be developed for teacher trainees.

References :

1. Briñol , P., Petty, R.E and D. D. Rucker (2006). The role of meta-cognitive processes in emotional intelligence. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 84, 1123-1139.
2. Borkowski, J., Carr, M., & Pressely, M. (1987). " Spontaneous " strategy use: Perspectives from metacognitive theory. *Intelligence*, 11, 61-75.
3. Brown, A. L. (1980). Metacognitive development and reading. In R. J. Spiro, B. C. Bruce, & W. F. Brewer (Eds.), *Theoretical issues in reading comprehension* (pp. 453-482). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
4. Brown, A. (1987). Metacognition, executive control, self-regulation and other more mysterious mechanisms. In F. E. Weinert , & R. H. Kluwe (Eds.). *Metacognition, motivation, and understanding*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
5. Flavell, J. H. (1976). Metacognitive aspects of problem solving. In: L. B. Resnick (Ed.). *The nature of intelligence*. (pp.231-235). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
6. Flavell, J. H. (1979). Metacognition and cognitive monitoring: A new area of cognitive developmental inquiry. *American Psychologist*, 34, 906-911.
7. Flavell, J. H. (1987). Speculations about the nature and development of metacognition. In F. E. Weinert, & R. H. Kluwe (Eds.), *Metacognition, motivation, and understanding*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
8. Kurtz, B. E., & Borkowski, J. G. (1984). Children's metacognition: Exploring relations among knowledge, process and motivational variables. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 57, 335-354.
9. Miller, J.W. (2000). "Exploring the Source of Self-Regulated Learning: The Influence of Internal and External Comparisons. *Journal of Instructional Psychology*. 27: 47-52.
10. Ozsoy , G., & Ataman, A. (2007). The effect of metacognitive strategy training on problem solving achievement. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 1 (2), 67-82.
11. Punita Govil (2006). 'Metacognition Inventory,' National Psychological Corporation, Agra.
12. Schömmer , M. (1993). Epistemological development and academic performance among secondary students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 85, 406-411.
13. Sternberg, R. J. (1986a). Inside intelligence. *American Scientist*, 74, 137-143.
14. Sternberg, R. J. (1986b). *Intelligence applied*. New York: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich, Publishers.
15. Sternberg, R. J. (1998). Metacognition, abilities, and developing expertise: What makes an expert student? *Instructional Science*, 26, 127-140.

